

Efficient Software for Archiving and Retrieving Results of Massive Bioinformatics Analyses in High-Performance Computing Environments

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Abstract—Modern sequencing and computational facilities in biomedical and agricultural areas generate and analyze hundreds or thousands of samples every day. At that scale production bioinformatics workflows can produce vast amounts of data, which need to be managed: organized, deleted, moved, stored, and retrieved. This can create an infrastructure bottleneck especially when moving or archiving data. The difficulty stems chiefly from the structure of file collections being produced: frequently very large number of files, with a highly nested directory structure, and a heterogeneous distribution of file sizes, with emphasis on large numbers of very small files. Parallel file systems, such as Lustre, GPFS, and tape archives, can perform poorly under these circumstances due to overabundance of metadata. However, standard packaging utilities, such as tar and zip, do not scale well with the size of the data for this particular use case. The present manuscript reviews several recently developed parallel alternatives, showcasing their performance on a variety of high performance computing systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern file systems for High Performance Computing (HPC), particularly Lustre, are designed to perform well with moderate numbers of very large files and they do so admirably. Traditional HPC workloads, such as physics, astrophysics, chemistry, computational fluid dynamics, and other engineering applications, structure their I/O operations to take advantage of this architecture. However, a large fraction of software in bioinformatics [1–4] are relatively new to HPC environments and not yet structured to make best use of parallel file systems.

These bioinformatics applications were originally designed to be deployed on a local desktop or small cluster, and be run on small datasets of a few samples at a time, generating a few GB of data per run. In that local environment producing numerous small files did not cause problems. However, when deployed in parallel on hundreds and thousands of samples in an HPC environment [1, 5].

At that scale small files are generated in the millions, sometimes in quick bursts, which can create real computational bottlenecks on parallel file systems. The problem is created by the need to string multiple applications, each responsible for a different part of the analysis, together into a single workflow. Each application will generate output files, which will serve as an input to the next step, generating many concurrent metadata requests that can flood and overwhelm the file system. Converting these complex workflows into

monolithic applications would eliminate the intermediary data, alleviating the problem. Such effort is ongoing [6–9].

However, the field of computational biology continues to evolve very rapidly, and the analysis algorithms are still being reworked, adjusted and optimized to improved accuracy. Thus proliferation of individual software applications continues, hampering the adoption of any monolithic workflows that may be released in the meantime. We predict that complex multi-step workflows that produce numerous files will continue to be run in HPC for a while yet, and a good solution for file management when archiving or moving data is needed.

One straightforward way to deal with archiving or transferring large numbers of files is to group data files into container files the way Unix tar [10] or similar tools do. This works for smaller collections of small files. However, for collections of files that are tens or hundreds of GB for the whole collection, tar, which is single-threaded, can take an uncomfortably long time. For example, packaging up an Arabidopsis directory (described later in this document) with a single-threaded Unix tar may take more than 5 hours even in current HPC system (see Table III). For specific HPC systems aggressively tuned for large files, the amount of time required to use single-threaded tar to aggregate those collections is longer than allowed by the cluster’s execution policy. Other file packaging tools, including pigz [11] and ptar [12], are multi-threaded for compressing the data, but do not use multiple nodes in a cluster environment to take advantage of parallel file systems. Since the problem is the file system bottleneck to a single computational node, those tools do not help in any significant way.

The NCSA Genomics Group running their analyses on Blue Waters ran into these scaling problems multiple times. The file handling difficulty impacted their workflows as well as others on the system by slowing down the overall file system speed. To combat this, The Genomics Team and Blue Waters user support team independently developed three different parallel tar-like applications to address the problem of multiple file storage: “ptgz”, “mpitar” and “parfu”. Each tool initially focused on a different aspect of the bottleneck observed when creating archives of large collections of files: Ptgz on the CPU resources required for compression, mpitar on file access delays, and parfu on bulk parallel IO performance. This paper reports on the design and structure of these codes, and also

reports performance tests we ran on several different HPC platforms with representative genomics data sets. The team also archived the same data sets with tar and some common tar variants for performance comparisons, and their the results are reported.

The remainder of the manuscript is organized as follows. In section II we discuss existing file archiving tools and their shortcomings when used on large, parallel file systems. In section V we describe the test setup and metrics used to compare different file archiving tools. In section IV we provide a short description of the codes we developed and tested. In Section VI we review archiving performance results obtained on different HPC systems. Finally in sections VII and VIII we discuss results and future efforts.

II. MOTIVATION

This section details the systems on Blue Waters that were impacted by workloads that produced volumes of extremely numerous files. These impacts, and the inadaquacy of the stock file aggregation tools in the next section led to our developing the parallel file aggregation tools featured in this paper.

A. Parallel Disk File Systems (*Lustre*)

A Lustre file system setup consists of Metadata Server (MDS) and Object Storage Servers (OSS) [13]. Connected to the MDS and OSSs are multiple Metadata Target (MDT) and Object Storage Target (OST) that contain the actual storage units holding data. The metadata servers hold and process information about the file system structure, i.e., the directories and files in existence, access permissions, quota, and which OSSs serves the actual data stored in a file. In Lustre versions before 2.21, only one of the MDS is *active* and accepts requests by client applications while the other MDS serve as *failover* servers for the active one. Lustre 2.12, released December 2018, partially address these issues, but as of this writing we have not been able to test on a system with a Lustre file system that new. This impacts the ability of a Lustre based file system handling many concurrent metadata requests that need to be handled by the MDS. This contrasts with bulk data operations that are served by the OSSs and do not suffer from the same many-to-one relation between clients and server(s).

B. Tape Storage Systems (*HPSS*)

All the systems we tested this software on, as is typical of large systems, have a tape library that stores user's data for later retrieval and re-use (storage for more than a certain length of time, or more than the user's group disk quota). Users use storage tools to move data from mounted disks on the system to the tape storage, where it initially resides in disk cache. The tape storage system then asynchronously moves those user files from the disk cache off to individual tapes as tape drives and tapes become available. The strength of this approach is the user does the movement synchronously, but moving data to tape storage takes place asynchronously and so can be scheduled and done efficiently in the background.

When the user goes to request the files again, the storage system mounts the tapes where the files reside, copies the files back to the disk cache, and then on to where the user specified the retrieved files to go. This again works well; the only delays are that retrieving files requires synchronous access to the tape drives in the storage system. If the system is busy, files will take longer to retrieve, but all files still should be retrieved in a reasonable amount of time.

There is a weakness to these HPSS storage systems that users have encountered, and the support team are working on ways to mitigate. There are certain work-flows (examples include gene sequence comparisons and astronomy image processing) that produce many many comparatively small files. Some of our user's work-flows have produce directories containing over 30 million files from the workflow for a single scientific problem.

Those collections of numerous files can be staged to storage disk cache very efficiently; they tend to transfer very fast. Since the files are small, the tape system can transfer the files to tape very quickly. However, in moving many many small files to many many different tapes, the storage of a single data set becomes tremendously fragmented. Retrieving this data then depends on how fast single tapes can be mounted and read for very very small files. In many cases for our users, the times to read the file collection would take longer than the global timeout for the retrieval.

C. Long-Distance File Transfers

The overriding motivation for developing fast, parallel aggregation tools at NCSA were impacts to parallel file system and effects on tape archives. However, moving file collections from site to site was also a use case that millions of file collections also made difficult. Globus, for instance, parallelizes file transfers, but only up to a certain number (typically 64) of simultaneous files. If a file collection consists of millions of files, transferring such a collection could easily take many weeks, due to the latency of the startup and teardown of all the individual transfers. This was not the main driving use case for our file aggregation tools, but this is a use case that was effected profoundly by having fast, paralle file aggregation tools.

III. EXISTING FILE AGGREGATION TOOLS

File aggregation is an explored software technology. Users on Blue Waters used these file aggregation tools to package files to combat the problems listed in the previous section. However, these tools were not suitable or available or fast enough (or created yet), which drove the creation of the codes featured in this paper.

A. File Aggregation Tools Used for Comparisons

We used these standard, widely available file aggregation tools for performance comparisons later in this paper.

Blue Waters users tested other file aggregation tools, including pigz [11] and ptar [12]. Both of those tools are multi-threaded, but they do not use multiple nodes in a cluster

environment to take advantage of parallel file systems. Since the real problem we have is the file system bottleneck to a single computational node, those tools do not help in any significant way.

B. Other File Aggregation Tools

This section lists file aggregation tools that exist, but for one reason or another we did not use for performance comparisons in this work.

1) *Pltar*: In the process of preparing for this paper, we ran across a tool developed by Oak Ridge National Lab and mentioned in a Cray User’s Group paper [14] in 2010, that seems to be a tool that is targeted at this sort of problem [15]. That tool is called “*pltar*”. Other than those two papers, we were not able to find any evidence that *pltar* has been published for others to use. We contacted the authors of the 2010 CUG paper [14] at ORNL, and they confirmed that *pltar* had not been released and is not available.

2) *Fcp*: Oak Ridge National Lab also developed “*fcp*”, a tool for fast copies of data from two different file systems. *fcp* takes advantage of HPC environments with the ability to employ multiple nodes to increase performance of file transfer. Initial results from the Oak Ridge National Lab demonstrated high scalability as node count increased with varying scalability with increases in stripe count dependent on dataset size. *fcp* also implements live checksumming to preserve transfer progress in the event of a failure.

3) *Dtar*: We have not included comparisons to the “*dtar*” tool that is a part of the *mpiFileUtils* [16, 17] implementation that has very recently be released. Previous versions of *mpiFileUtils* code had listed *dtar* as “experimental” only, not to be used for production, and earlier versions of *dtar* were listed as single-threaded. The current release of *mpiFileUtils* lists *dtar* as “production”, so in future work we will need to test it against these applications. However, when the latest *mpiFileUtils* was released, the performance comparisons were well finished and comparison of this manuscript was well under way.

4) *Htar*: *Htar* is an application that bundles files into tar files as part of archiving to a tape system. *htar*[18–21] is various implementations of Unix tar like tools that have specific OS-specific or site-specific access to tape systems. *Htar* is used as a front end for users to archive directory trees of files together while moving the data onto archival tape systems. *Htar* is not a generic performance-enhancing tool, it is tar interfaced to a specific tape archive systems on its back end. As such it is tied to site and vendor tape solutions, and not a general-purpose portable tool like *ptgz*, *mpitar* or *parfu* are. For this reason we did not include it in the set of tools we compared.

IV. DEVELOPED CODES

This section details the codes developed as a part of this work. Broadly, *Ptgz* uses the pre-existing tar command and parallelizes file aggregation and compression using temporary

Fig. 1. Functional overview of *mpitar*, and its file format. The file format is identical to GNU tar. Not shown here is each embedded file has a header listing its characteristics.

output files, *mpitar* is designed to minimize metadata operations and is designed for collections of many small files, and *parfu* parallelizes both per-file I/O and multi-file I/O operations.

A. Ptgz

“*Ptgz*” is a MPI parallel archiving tool developed by the NCSA Genomics Group for internal use [22]. *Ptgz* leverages the existing Unix tar utility by implementing a MPI parallel driver code that controls multiple tar instances to produce intermediate, inner, tar archives which are then combined into a single, outer, tar archive.

During archive creation the manager process creates a catalog of all files to be archived. Files in this catalog are then randomly but statically assigned to worker processes to be processed by tar into one intermediate tar archive for each worker process. Random assignment of files avoids issues of consecutive files being clustered on the same storage server and was found to improve speed compared to algorithms that attempt to balance archive size among the worker processes. At this point *gzip* [23] compression is applied to the data to reduce overall file size. For the text based comma separated value (csv) files used by current genomics applications, compression using *gzip*’s fastest compression level, results in up to 40% reduction in file size. For large sets of files performance is typically limited by read speed of the many small files, thus hiding the time spent compressing. This step is currently not multi-threaded though thread-parallel *gzip* implementations exist [11] and could be used immediately if required. In the final step the intermediate tar files, as well as an index file recording each intermediate tar file’s content, are combined into the final tar file archive.

During extraction the reverse process is applied by first extracting the index file and inner tar archives from the outer archive, then extract all data from the inner archives.

B. Mpitar

“*Mpitar*” is a parallel archiver that produces archive files in POSIX tar format (PAX). Fig. 1 shows the basic concepts used in *mpitar*’s design. It targets shared, parallel file systems on compute clusters that typically provide very high bulk transfer

speeds much higher than found on typical desktop computer but at the same time may be severely limited in their metadata operation performance when compared to those same desktop computers.

Mpitar is written in C++ and uses MPI and the POSIX pthread library for parallelization. It is available under the NCSA license [24].

Mpitar’s design assumes that metadata activities, i.e. file open and close operations rather than bulk transfer are the dominant cost. It further assumes that there is a single metadata server such that concurrent metadata operations will not result in a speedup. It also assumes that there are multiple servers for bulk data operations, a situation often true on Lustre based filesystems.

To cope with this situation mpitar uses a manager / worker setup in which a single manager scans for files to include in the archive and assigns them to workers. Mpitar defines the concept of a work package that is defined as either a set number of files or a set of files whose aggregate size exceeds a chosen threshold. Importantly, files are assigned to only one work package, i.e. there is no parallelism within a single file. Once the manager has collected enough files to form a work package it assigns the work package to an idle worker. It then continues to scan for files assigning work packages to workers in a round robin manner. To avoid situations where a single worker is assigned all “slow” work packages, there is a maximum number of waiting work packages for each worker. Once this limit is reached, no more packages are assigned to this worker. Workers in turn signal the manager once they have finished a work package which triggers the master to assign a new package to the worker. Each worker is a multi-threaded process consisting of a reader / communicator thread and a writer thread. The reader thread accepts work packages from the master and reads data for the files in the work package from disk. Each reader thread uses a ring-buffer to send data to its associated writer thread which writes data to the archive file, thus overlapping read and write calls to the file system. The size of the ring buffer is fixed, and the ring buffer is capable of seeking in the output file without having to flush the buffer.

Mpitar strives to reduce metadata activity as much as possible. For example only the manager calls the `stat` system call to acquire information about a file’s size and type. It uses the information to decide where in the archive to place each file and whether the file is in fact a directory that must be recursed into. The manager passes this information to the workers as part of their work packages. Similarly workers will only `seek` to a new location at the beginning of a work package as files in a single work package form a contiguous block in the output archive.

To facilitate retrieval of individual files from the archive, mpitar constructs an index files which records the location of each file in the archive. This file is stored at the end of the archive. Mpitar provides a number of Perl tools to extract this index file from the end of the archive without scanning the whole archive and to extract a subset of files given their

Fig. 2. Functional overview of parfu, and its file format. The file format is identical to GNU tar, but the first embedded “file” is a catalog of the entire container file, and there are blank files for padding. Not shown here is each embedded file has a header listing its characteristics, as in GNU tar.

associated offsets in the archive file.

In its current form mpitar does not employ any collective MPI-I/O calls for reading or writing, instead each worker acts independently of the others. Since mpitar does not take attempt to limit bulk I/O activity a large number of worker targeting files residing on a single storage server have the potential to overwhelm that server, reducing overall speed.

Similarly mpitar does not currently offer any extraction either as serial or parallel functionality. Such extraction is left to the existing POSIX tar command.

C. Parfu

“Parfu” is an MPI archive tool, essentially a parallel MPI-enabled multi-node implementation of tar. Fig. 2 shows the basic concepts used in parfu’s design.

It is designed to run in a cluster environment reading from and writing to parallel file systems. Parfu produces files that are tar-compatible archives. The archive files can be unpacked with conventional Unix tar.

Parfu begins by making a catalog of all the files to be archived. This internal list of files is sorted by file size and broadcast to all of the ranks in the parfu instance to minimize blocking inter-process communication. All the data about what files will be archived is collected once at the beginning of execution by rank 0 of the application.

1) *File Blocking*: Parfu stores target files in the container file starting on “block” boundaries in order to maximize the efficiency of the data readers and writers and minimize lock contention on the parallel file system. The term “block” here is an organizational parameter internal to parfu, and has nothing to do with hardware block sizes on disk. This creates voids in the container file. The voids in the container file have tar header sections inserted so that tar will unpack them. All the voids have the same name, so when they are unpacked by tar they result in only one spurious “space” file.

Larger target files occupy many blocks in the parfu container file. Smaller files only occupy a single block. To minimize the waste of reserving one block for every constituent file to be stored, the block size is dynamic. The minimum block size is set at compile time as of the current version of parfu. In future versions, this minimum will be configurable with a

TABLE I
OVERVIEW OF CLUSTERS AND FILE SYSTEMS USED TO TEST ARCHIVING TOOLS. CORES AND RAM ARE LISTED ON A PER-NODE BASIS.

System	File system	Processor	Cores	RAM, GB
iForge	GPFS	Skylake	40	192
Stampede 2	Lustre	Skylake	48	192
Blue Waters	Lustre	Interlagos	32	64

command line parameter. This parameter may be important for performance of parfu while packaging up directory trees of very small files.

2) *Tar File Interoperability of Parfu Archive Files*: Parfu writes archive files in a format is constructed as a Unix-tar-compatible file, and can be read by Unix tar out of the box. Parfu produces a separate catalog that lists the constituent files. The catalog is inserted into the resulting archive file as if it was a text file containing the archive information, so if tar is used to unpack a parfu archive, the index file will be unpacked into the target directory (named “.parfu_index” and since most Unix shells hide files that being with “.” by default, most users won’t even notice the index file is there.)

Parfu separates stored files farther apart with “pad” files consisting of zeros for efficiency and simplicity of storage. The file padding is to guarantee that constituent files are read and written by the same rank of the application, unless larger than a certain threshold, in which case they’re written by multiple ranks. This feature is will probably be removed in the upcoming upgrade of parfu to C++, in progress in the fall of 2021.

V. PERFORMANCE TESTING SETUP

This section lists the HPC systems we tested both the reference tools and our developed tools on, outlines the bioinformatics test data we used as our standard data sets, and the testing procedures we used.

A. Test Systems

Lustre and GPFS are parallel file systems that are widely used in HPC but differ in how they handle metadata and I/O parallelism. We tested the performance of archiving software packages in relation to these file systems, by executing them on multiple compute clusters (Table I).

a) *iForge*: is an Industry Group supercomputer at the National Center for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA), and runs GPFS [25] as a production file system. At the time of testing the system utilized Skylake Xeon Gold 6148 processors (2.40 GHz). Each node had 192 GB, 2.67GHz RAM. The stateless nodes ran Red Hat Enterprise Linux 6.9, connected to a network-attached IBM GPFS (ver. 4.2) with custom metadata acceleration. The metadata were stored on NVME drives replicated across the core I/O servers, and small files (<168b) were stored within the inodes. Interconnect was provided via EDR InfiniBand with 100 Gb/sec bandwidth and 100 ns latency.

TABLE II
FILE COUNTS AND TOTAL SIZE FOR THE THREE BIOINFORMATICS DATA SETS USED IN TESTING THE FILE AGGREGATION TOOLS.

Data Set	Number of Files	Total Size
GWAS	198,281	27 GB
Arabdiopsis	1,423,280	492 GB
VarCall	2027	732 GB

b) *Stampede 2*: is a Lustre-based cluster administered by the Texas Advanced Computing Center. We used nodes with Intel Xeon Platinum 8160 (“Skylake”) processors running at a clock speed of 2.1GHz nominal. The Skylake nodes have 48 cores in two CPU sockets and 192GB (2.67GHz) DDR4 RAM. Nodes are interconnected via a 100Gb/sec Intel Omni-Path (OPA) network with a fat tree topology employing six core switches. Stampede’s production 30PB (scratch) file system uses Lustre with 66 OST and and aggregate bandwidth of > 300GB/s. It uses 4 MDS.

Blue Waters is a large Cray XE/XK cluster administered by NCSA. It contains 26864 compute nodes, 22636 of which are dual-socket AND 6276 Interlagos nodes with 32 cores and 64GB (1.6GHz) DDR3 RAM. Nodes are connected via a 76.8Gb/sec Cray Gemini network with nodes arranged in a mesh in a 3D torus. Blue Waters’s production 22PB (scratch) file system uses Lustre with 360 OST and an aggregate bandwidth of > 1.1TB/s. An active / passive MDS setup is used with the single active MDS serving all 26864 compute nodes.

B. Test Data

Different bioinformatics input data sets with different file size distributions (see Table II) were used to determine scalability of all the applications, included different file distributions to measure variations in performance. The first, referred to “VarCall” in this paper, was synthetic variant calling data derived from whole-genome sequencing with 30× coverage. It possessed an L-shaped distribution of file sizes resulting from few large files and many small files. The second data set, referred to as “GWAS” in this paper, was variant calling data for forty soybean samples [26], and the third was Arabidopsis lyrata data, “Arabidopsis” in this paper. File size distribution differences across different input data sets were reflective of various genomic analyses results [27] and were used to determine the performance of all the file packaging tools the different computing systems.

C. Testing Procedure

To ensure comparable and reproducible results, all tests were automated via a Perl script, available in the parfu github repository. It generated batch jobs appropriately for the scheduler commands and file paths of each compute cluster. We ran two batches of tests. First, on iForge we wanted to take the baseline (1 node runs) and understand how the three software packages (introduced in section VI) compared to each other and to standard tools when run in the most likely production scenario using 4 compute nodes, which is sufficient

to gain a significant speedup yet not very costly in terms of allocation hours. Mpitar and parfu were found to perform the best, and were chosen them for further scalability analysis on Stampede 2 and Blue Waters. In that second set of tests we varied input file collections, number of nodes used and number of ranks used per node.

Each parallel application on each machine was initially run on one node with different numbers of ranks on all the file sets. The number of ranks with the shortest time (fastest) for that application across all three data sets was picked as the ranks-per-node for that application for all scale testing on that system. That ensured that the best ranks-per-node setting was used for every application, to show the best performance for each application on that system.

Performance was measured as the total rate of data transfer (GB/s) as a function of the number of nodes. All tests were run in three sequential trials to account for possible variability due to the cluster load, however the differences among replicates were found to be negligible.

Fig. V-C shows the testing commands as they were run in the testing run scripts.

VI. RESULTS

This section contains experimental results of the performance comparisons between the three developed codes and other similar tools.

A. Walltime Benchmarks and Comparisons

All the file packaging applications were run archiving each of the three data sets with multiple configurations with multiple trials to blend over statistical anomalies. All of the parallel applications were also run first on one node and then multiple nodes to check the scaling. The first runs were run on the iForge system at the University of Illinois. These iForge runs were used to benchmark the codes against each other and the measure the effectiveness with the different file sets. The data from the iForge runs are shown in Table III. These data are shown in tabular rather than graphical form because there are so many different variable combinations that graphs become difficult to interpret.

Most of the applications were then run for scaling tests on Blue Waters at NCSA and on Stampede 2 at TACC. Some of the applications were not run on those machines or at large scales, either due to runtime problems on those systems or in some cases the runtimes were too long to complete enough trials to measure. All successful runs that were verified to produce valid and readable archives are included in these graphs. Any missing data are due to runs that did not complete.

Figs. 5, 6, and 7 show the total archive rate of the file archiving codes as a function of number of nodes, one graph per data set on Stampede 2. These graphs show the vast advantage of the parallel solutions over single-threaded tar. Mpitar and parfu scale similarly up to 16 nodes but seem to both be saturating at that scale. mpitar stays close to twice as fast as parfu across the node scaling and for all the data sets.

TABLE III
APPLICATION PERFORMANCE ON THE iFORGE SYSTEM IN TABULAR FORM. PERFORMANCE ON GWAS, THEN ARABIDOPSIS, THEN VARCALL FROM TOP TO BOTTOM. WITHIN EACH SECTION BY DATA SET, THE TOP SECTION HAS THE STANDARD LEGACY TOOLS TO COMPARE TO AND THE LOWER SECTION HAS THE PARALLEL TOOLS THAT ARE THE SUBJECT OF THIS PAPER.

Code	Data	Nodes	Transfer Time (s)	Rate (MB/s)	Rate Per Node (MB/s/node)
tar	GWAS	1	496	54	54
tar+gz	GWAS	1	3756	7	7
pigz	GWAS	1	5499	5	5
ptgz	GWAS	1	132	204	204
ptgz	GWAS	4	128	210	52
mpitar	GWAS	1	122	220	220
mpitar	GWAS	4	45	596	149
parfu	GWAS	1	39	681	681
parfu	GWAS	4	23	1163	291
tar	Arabidopsis	1	19634	25	25
tar+gz	Arabidopsis	1	52825	9	9
ptgz	Arabidopsis	1	1981	248	248
ptgz	Arabidopsis	4	2025	243	61
mpitar	Arabidopsis	1	2483	198	198
mpitar	Arabidopsis	4	639	769	192
parfu	Arabidopsis	1	795	619	619
parfu	Arabidopsis	4	342	1436	359
tar	VarCall	1	2176	336	336
tar+gz	VarCall	1	23448	31	31
mpitar	VarCall	1	2871	255	255
mpitar	VarCall	4	5962	123	31
parfu	VarCall	1	289	2527	2527
parfu	VarCall	4	108	6778	1694

Figs. 8, 9, and 10 graph the performance of all the applications for GWAS, Arabidopsis, and VarCALL (respectively) on Blue Waters.

B. Node Scalability Analysis

Figs. 11, 12, and 13 illustrate the scalability of the applications on Stampede 2. These scaling graphs don't depict absolute performance at all. The value at 1 node is defined as equal to 1. All subsequent points are calculated as the archive rate at that scale, divided by the product of the archive rate at the previous point times two. A scaling value of 1 means perfect scaling; double the nodes doubled the application performance. A scaling value of 0.5 indicates perfectly poor scaling; doubling the number of nodes didn't improve the overall application performance. A value of around or above 0.7 indicates reasonable scaling. For all three data sets, parfu and mpitar scale decently well up to 4 nodes, but poorly after 8 nodes, and scaling at 8 nodes is marginal, and dependent on the data set.

Finally, Figs. 14, 15, and 16 are the scaling graphs as above, but for the Blue Waters system. As on Stampede, the numerous-file data sets (GWAS and Arabidopsis) both mpitar and scale decently well through four nodes, but then drop off in per-node performance. Both codes scaled decently up to 8 nodes on VarCall, again probably due to the larger file distribution.

```

tar cf /arcv/dir/arcv_file.tar /target/dir/
tar cf - /target/dir/ | gzip --fast - > /arcv/dir/arcv_file.tgz
pigz -K -r --stdout /target/dir/ > output_file.zip

ptgz -c -d /target/dir/ arcv_file_stub_name
mpitar -f /arcv/dir/arcv_file.tar -c /target/dir/
parfu C /arcv/dir/arcv_file.pfu /target/dir/

```

Fig. 3. This table lists how the various commands were invoked in our run scripts. The lines represent: (stock comparison codes) tar, tar-gz, and pigz; and codes featured in this paper: ptgz, mpitar, and parfu.

Fig. 4. Packaging tool performance on iForge. Shown are transfer rates in MB/s for the GWAS data set. Tar, tar+gz and pigz, being non-MPI-parallel, are only shown for 1 node.

Fig. 5. GWAS on Stampede 2, total archive rate. Mpitar: red triangles, dotted line; parfu: green squares, solid line; ptgz: cyan hexagon; tar: magenta star; tar-gz: purple circle.

C. Real-world Success Stories

Blue Waters support staff have already used parfu in packaging up user’s many-file data into large archive files to ease moving simulation data off the system in the last few months of the NSF phase of the system. As an example [28]: “PK Yeung and the NFS PRAC allocation for ‘A Penultimate Petascale Computational Laboratory for Turbulence and Mag-

Fig. 6. Arabidopsis on Stampede 2, total archive rate. Mpitar: red triangles, dotted line; parfu: green squares, solid line; ptgz: cyan hexagon, solid cyan line; tar: magenta star.

Fig. 7. VarCall on Stampede 2, total archive rate. Mpitar: red triangles, dotted line; parfu: green squares, solid line; ptgz: cyan hexagon, solid cyan line; tar: magenta star.

Fig. 8. GWAS on Blue Waters, total archive rate. Mpitar: red triangles, dotted line; parfu: green squares, solid line.

Fig. 9. Arabidopsis on Blue Waters, total archive rate. Mpitar: red triangles, dotted line; parfu: green squares, solid line.

Fig. 10. VarCall on Blue Waters, total archive rate. Mpitar: red triangles, dotted line; parfu: green squares, solid line.

Fig. 11. Scaling performance graph for GWAS on Stampede 2. Both codes scale reasonably well (scaling value approximate 0.7 or above) through 8 nodes, but scale poorly at 16 nodes. Mpitar: red triangles, dotted line; parfu: green squares, solid line; ptgz: cyan hexagon; tar: magenta star; tar+gz: purple circle.

Fig. 12. Scaling performance graph for Arabidopsis on Stampede 2. For this data set, the codes scale well through 4 nodes, but not to 8 nodes. (The anomalously high value for mpitar at 16 nodes we presume is because of the probably anomalously low performance value at 8 nodes, which skews the variation between 8 and 16). Mpitar: red triangles, dotted line; Parfu: green squares, solid line; ptgz: cyan hexagon, solid cyan line; tar: magenta star.

netohydrodynamic Turbulence’ thank the Blue Waters collaboration for their assistance in moving our simulation results off the Blue Waters system at the end of our experimental runs. Our simulation snapshots consist of directories of files 4 TB each. The parfu aggregation tool developed by the Blue Waters support team allowed us to package up our files so they were easy to transport to other systems.”

VII. DISCUSSION

The data from Stampede 2 for archiving the GWAS data set (the smallest of the three) exhibited a curious artifact that we recognised and then had to change our data analysis methodology to compensate for. It seems that something in

Fig. 13. Scaling performance graph for Variant Calling on Stampede 2. Mpitar scales well up to 4 nodes, parfu up to 8 nodes. Mpitar: red triangles, dotted line. Parfu: green squares, solid line. ptgz: cyan hexagon, solid cyan line, tar: magenta star.

Fig. 15. Arabidopsis on Blue Waters, archive rate per node. Mpitar: red triangles, dotted line; parfu: green squares, solid line.

Fig. 14. Scaling performance for GWAS on Blue Waters. Mpitar: red triangles, dotted line; parfu: green squares, solid line.

Fig. 16. Variant Calling on Blue Waters, archive rate per node. Mpitar: red triangles, dotted line; parfu: green squares, solid line.

the file system cached either some of the data or (more likely) some of the metadata from some of the runs. The manifestation of this effect was that the runtime for each iteration after the first in a single job with multiple iterations would be much shorter than the first iteration. Our interpretation of this effect is that the first lookup of the information pulled it into a cache of some sort, so it was still available at cache level for the second and subsequent iterations in that same job. We filtered this data out at the analysis level, because having data already in cache is not a realistic speed test for an application. No caching effects were observed on iForge or Blue Waters. Our allocation on TACC systems ran out before we could further investigate this phenomenon and characterize it.

A. Features Roadmap and Limitations

1) Ptgz:

a) *Direct Storage Of Compressed Data In Target File:* Ptgz currently uses intermediate, compressed tar files that are combined into a single final tar file in the final step of archive building. This implies that all data is written twice resulting in a slowdown even when considering the faster bulk IO operation used when combining the intermediate files compared to the slower, smaller IO operations used when creating them. In conjunction with work towards supporting compression in parfu and mpitar, removing the need for these temporary files will make ptgz more competitive in its performance.

b) *Limitations:* Ptgz relies on the existing Unix tar command to build its intermediate archives. It is thus limited to tar's performance and cannot easily take advantage of non-POSIX features available in the file system, that may be exposed only through the MPI-IO API. Similarly some MPI stacks impose constraints on using the `system` call and starting new processes which can prevent ptgz from successfully starting tar

on HPC systems using those MPI stacks.

2) *Mpitar*:

a) *Per File Parallelism*: Mpitar does not use multiple IO streams for a single file included in an archive. For collections of files with a number very large files this was observed to be a bottleneck and we intent to port the parallel stream code used in *parfu* to *mpitar*.

b) *File Extraction*: The most obvious missing feature in *mpitar* is currently its lack of file extraction capability. Given the information stored in the catalog file extraction is parallelizable as long as directories and symbolic links used in file paths are created before the files themselves. In the absence of type and symbolic link target information in the catalog files the manager process must ensure that files are only passed to workers for extractions once all path components exist.

3) *Parfu*:

a) *File Extraction*: The current test version of *parfu* only creates archives, it does not extract them. This needs to be fixed, and the near-future rollout will have the capability.

b) *Limitations*: *Parfu* is deliberately designed to collect the entire file and directory list before writing anything to the archive. This allows the file catalog to be written to the beginning of the *.pfu* container file, which will make it easy (once implemented) to determine the list of files in the container, and also to extract certain files without having to traverse the entire container to build a catalog. This is a design choice, which also artificially serializes the archive creation process, because currently the implementation is that rank 0 does all the file system querying. The C++ port (in progress in late 2021) may parallelize this process somewhat.

4) *Broadly Applicable Features and Limitations*: This section lists limitations common to more than one of the developed codes, or enhancements that could be applied to more than one, or all of them.

a) *Compression*: Compressing archive files would be a good upgrade for either *mpitar* or *parfu*.

Compression of archive files would entail yet another major step up in storage efficiency. However, it would require a significant design change and should be its own feature roll-out, separately from everything else. Small files can be compressed on a single rank, but compression of larger files and the best method for dividing files to archive before they are compressed present design challenges that will also affect current functionality.

Implementing compression in these codes will require careful performance and design studies. One possible way to implement compression would be to change how files are stored in the *parfu/mpitar* container, possibly up to and including using external libraries (*hdf5*, for instance). Trade-offs for the various methods of file compression will need to be studied.

b) *Single-threaded Metadata Collection*: *Mpitar* is limited to use a single process, the manager, to scan for files when building the archive. High performance file systems with a multiple metadata servers using fast storage may support parallel file listing which may increase performance for very large collections of files.

c) *Multi File Output*: A commonly requested feature of archive tools is to split generated the archive into smaller files, for example to allow different parts to be transferred independently to and from a tape archive system or to a remote file system. We plan to implement such a feature to generate multiple output files with a given maximum file size, each of which will be a self-contained tar archive each with its own catalog file along with a single full catalog file that describes all partial archive files and their content. Work towards this is already in progress.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

Bioinformatics (and other) workflows produce file collections that adversely impact the usability of high performance file systems on cluster computing systems. Having high-performance parallel file packaging tools can take up a lot of the slack in these workloads, relieving pressure on the file systems and file transfer mechanisms. *Ptgz*, *mpitar*, and *parfu* are all different design choices for such tools. In parallel, by running more than an order of magnitude faster than single-thread tools, they can be deployed on systems with this workload and greatly increase the efficiency of such workflows on large-scale computer systems.

We will continue to test and deploy these solutions on HPC systems that we use.

Supercomputer Centers manage and help their users manage the interface between the vendor-provided software and the application build and run software. By implementing solutions that benefit multiple user groups, a site can greatly improve the user experience of all their users with small amounts of effort, if directed carefully to specific efforts.

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